

UVAH

**RAPID METHOD FOR DELETING
GENES IN HUMAN
CYTOMEGALOVIRUS GENOME
USING BACTERIAL ARTIFICIAL
CHROMOSOME LAMBDA RED
RECOMBINATION**

Método rápido para deleccionar genes en
el genoma de Citomegalovirus Humano
utilizando el sistema de recombinación
Lambda Red en Cromosomas Artificiales
Bacterianos

**Máster Universitario en Microbiología Aplicada a Salud Pública e
Investigación de Enfermedades infecciosas**

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Alcalá de Henares, a 21 de octubre de 2020

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY	1
ABSTRACT	1
INTRODUCTION	2
HCMV biology	2
<i>Genome</i>	3
<i>Cell tropism and life cycle</i>	4
Epidemiology and pathology	5
Immune response against HCMV	6
<i>Innate response</i>	6
<i>Humoral response</i>	7
<i>Cellular response</i>	7
Treatments and Vaccines for HCMV	7
Bacterial Artificial Chromosomes (BACs) in HCM studies	8
AIM OF WORK	9
MATERIALS AND METHODS	10
Strains and media	10
Construction of parental strain: Transformation of <i>E. coli</i> DH5α λpir carrying the BAC with pKD46	10
Design of the Kanamycin resistant (Kan^R) cassette	11
Transformation of <i>E. coli</i> DH5α λpir+BAC+pKD46 strain with Kan^R cassette	13
Deletion verification	14
Viral production by transfection in HEK 293t and MRC-5 cells	17
RESULTS	19
Selection of candidate genes for deletion, oligonucleotides and recombinant HCMV generation	19
Recombinant HCMV validation	20
Transformation of UL8-Kan^R cassette by using electrocompetent <i>E. coli</i> cells for the electroporation	27
Recombinant virus production and propagation	28
DISCUSSION	29
CONCLUSIONS	32
REFERENCES	33
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	38

ABREVIATIONS

HCMV: Human Cytomegalovirus

HHV: Human Herpesvirus

DNA: Desoxirribonucleic Acid

RNA: Ribonucleic Acid

TAE: Tris Acetate EDTA

Amp: Ampicilin

Kan: Kanamicyn

Chl: Chloramphenicol

Kan^R: Kanamycin Resistance

LB: Luria-Bertani

SOC: Super Optimal Broth

SOT: Solid Organ Trasplant

ORF: Open Reading Frame

IE: Intermediate Early

E: Early

L: Late

gC: glycoprotein complex

UL: Unique Long region

US: Unique Short region

TR: Terminal Repeated sequences

IR: Intern Repeated sequences

AC: Assembly Complex

MIEP: Major Immediate Early Promoter

HSCT: Hematopoietic Stem Cell
Transplant

TLR: Toll-Like Receptors

NK: Natural Killer

HLA: Human Leukocyte Antigen

Ig: Inmunoglobulin

PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction

BAC: Bacterial Artificial Chromosome

OD: Optical Density

WT: Wild Type

GFP: Green Fluorescent Protein

ANEXO 3

D./D^a Pilar Pérez Romero, Estéfani García Ríos

CERTIFICA:

Que el trabajo titulado: rapid method for deleting genes in human cytomegalovirus genome using bacterial artificial chromosome lambda red recombination, ha sido realizado bajo mi dirección por el alumno/a D./D^a Julia Gata de Benito

Alcalá de Henares, a 16 de octubre de 2020

A handwritten signature in blue ink, enclosed within a large, horizontal oval shape. The name 'Estéfani García Ríos' is written in cursive.

Firmado:

SUMMARY

Cytomegalovirus (HCMV) is the largest DNA virus known able to infect humans. Cytomegalovirus belongs to the *Herpesviridae* family. HCMV establishes persistent infection due to its capacity to generate latency in the host cells. It causes severe diseases in immunocompromised patients, being the major cause of mortality in Solid Organ Transplant (SOT) patients. In addition, it causes severe complications in neonates, due to the transmission from the mother to the child during pregnancy, childbirth and through breastfeeding. HCMV genome includes around 200 predictive Open Reading Frames (ORFs) of which only 60 have a known function, classified as α (immediate Early), β (Early) and γ (Late) genes. Some of the encoded proteins are membrane proteins and are involved in the interaction with the cell receptor during the viral entry, participating in protein complexes: gC-I, including glycoprotein gB, gC-II, formed by gM/gN, gC-III formed by the trimer gH/gL/gO and pentameric complex formed by gH/gL/UL128/UL130/UL131. Additionally, there are other 20 different putative membrane proteins which functions are still unknown. In order to get a better understanding of the function of the membrane proteins during viral cell cycle, we have developed a rapid method for generating HCMV gene deletion mutants by using the λ -Red recombination system and to study the viral cycle/infection in the absence of the deleted gene. This knowledge can be used to develop new strategies against HCMV infection, and all the associated complications.

Abstract

Citomegalovirus (HCMV) es el virus más grande conocido capaz de infectar al ser humano. Perteneciente a la familia de los Betaherpesvirus, es un virus de DNA envuelto capaz de establecer latencia en el huésped. La infección por HCMV causa enfermedad severa en pacientes inmunocomprometidos, tales como los pacientes trasplantados de órgano sólido (SOT) y en los casos de infección congénita en neonatos. El genoma del HCMV tiene aproximadamente unas 200 ORFs de las que sólo se conoce la función de 60. Los genes se clasifican en genes α , β y γ . Algunas de las proteínas codificadas son proteínas de membrana involucradas en la interacción con los receptores celulares durante la entrada en las células participando en complejos de membrana: gC-I, formado por la glicoproteína B (gB); gC-II, formado por el dímero gM/gN; gC-III, formado por el trímero gH/gL/gO; y el complejo pentamérico gH/gL/UL128/UL130/UL131. Además, existen otras 20 proteínas putativas de membrana con función desconocida. Para comprender mejor la función de las proteínas de la membrana durante el ciclo viral, hemos desarrollado un método rápido para generar mutantes por delección del gen en el genoma de HCMV utilizando el sistema de recombinación λ -Red y estudiar el ciclo viral/infección en

ausencia de este gen. Este conocimiento se puede utilizar para desarrollar nuevas estrategias contra la infección por HCMV y todas las complicaciones asociadas.

Keywords: Cytomegalovirus, Homologous recombination, Bacmid, electroporation, gene deletion, viral production

INTRODUCTION

HCMV biology

Cytomegalovirus (HCMV) belongs to *Herpesviridae* family, *Betaherpesvirinae* subfamily, *Cytomegalovirus* gender and Human herpesvirus 5 (HHV-5) specie ¹. It is the longest virus with the ability to infect to the human species ². HCMV consist of an icosaedric nucleocapsid that contains the double-stranded DNA genome, surrounded by the tegument, a proteic layer that includes the majority of the viral proteins, among them the pp65 protein (UL83), which is the most abundant protein in the tegument ². The lipid bilayer membrane is surrounding the tegument, which includes viral membrane proteins involved in the virus/cell interaction during the infection ^{1,3}. The membrane proteins are organized in four distinct glycoprotein complexes (gC): gC-I, formed by a homotrimer of glycoprotein B (UL55) which is involved in the fusion process during cell entry; gC-II, including gM (UL100) and gN (UL73) bound by a disulphide link, involved in the attachment of the virus to the host cell; gC-III (trimeric complex), a heterotrimer composed of the dimer gH/gL (UL75/UL115) bound by a sulphide link to gO (UL74). The dimer gH/gL takes part of the cell fusion machinery, while the trimer with gO seems to play a role in infection of virion-free cells ⁴. And finally, the pentameric complex (pC) composed of gH/ UL128, UL139 and UL131 which is required for entry in epithelial cells, myeloid cells, endothelial cells and leukocytes ^{4,5}.

Figure 1. Cytomegalovirus structure. HCMV is integrated by a nucleocapsid containing the dsDNA. Outside the capsid, it is the tegument surrounded by the lipid bilayer, were viral glycoproteins are located.

Genome

Cytomegalovirus has the largest genome within the Herpesviridae family. It is composed by 240 Kb with approximately 200 Open Reading Frames (ORFs) coding for more than 170 proteins^{1,6}. Two different segments can be distinguished (Figure 2A): L segment and S segment. Each segment is included in one region, forming the Unique Long region (UL) and the Unique Short region (US) flanked by the Terminal Repeated sequence (TR) and the Intern Repeated sequence (IR)^{1,7}. In addition, HCMV genome includes other sections that generate non-coding polyadenylated RNA antisense to the coding region and non-coding non-polyadenylated RNA with regulatory activity⁸. There are differences between different strains at both nucleotide and aminoacid levels, that result in different genotypes, but they are not different enough to distinguish serotypes³.

Figure 2. UL and US regions are separated by the TR and IR sequences. The protein expression cascade starts with genes α , which expresses IE proteins; continued, genes β expresses E proteins; finally, genes γ expresses L proteins. Figure adapted from S. Sanbonmatsu Gámez et al (2014)¹

Cell tropism and life cycle

HCMV has multiple cell tropism able to infect epithelial cells (main target during natural infection), endothelial cells and fibroblast and smooth muscle cells⁹. In contrast, HCMV has not the ability to replicate in myeloid cells, while it can be transported without replication in polymorphic leukocytes and establish latency in CD34+ progenitor hematopoietic cells¹⁰.

Entry of the virus in the cells occurs through the interaction of the envelope glycoproteins with the receptor in the cell surface which depends on the cell type. Infection of fibroblasts occurs in an independent-pH fusion manner that involves gH/gL dimer (Figure 3A). Virus entry into endothelial and epithelial cells occurs through a dependent-pH process mediated by endosomes that involves the pentameric complex¹¹ (Figure 3B).

Figure 3. Entry of HCMV in the cells by different pathways. (A) Fibroblast, HCMV can enter by pH-independent fusion and macropinocytosis-like pathways; (B) Epithelial cells, HCMV can enter by pH-dependent endocytosis or macropinocytosis-like pathways. Figure from Sandonís, García-Ríos, McConnell & Pérez-Romero, 2020

The capsids containing the viral genome are liberated into the cytoplasm and transported to the nuclear membrane where the DNA is injected to the nucleus. Protein expression occurs in a temporal cascade. The expression starts with α or Immediate Early (IE) genes, followed by the β or Early (E) genes and finally the γ or Late (L) genes (Figure 2B). DNA replication is produced between Early and Late phases ^{3,8}. Late genes encode the proteins for capsid assembly in the nucleus, and tegument proteins are acquired later in the cytoplasm. The virus acquires the viral envelope in the assembly complex (AC), formed by the endosomal machinery, the Golgi apparatus and the endoplasmic reticulum. Viral particles (along with non-infectious dense bodies) are released to the extracellular space ¹² (Figure 4).

Figure 4. HCMV life cycle. HCMV enters in the cell by fusion or endocytosis depending on the cell type. Replication occurs in the DNA and capsid formation after L genes translation. After encapsidation, viral envelope is acquiring in the assembly complex, and viral particles and dense bodies release the cell by exocytosis.

Epidemiology and pathology

HCMV is highly prevalent around the world ranging between 40 and 100% depending on social-economic factors among different regions ¹⁶. In 2019 it was estimated a global seroprevalence of 83%, with the highest seroprevalence located in the eastern Mediterranean (90%), and the lowest seroprevalence in the European region (66%). Within the population, women prevalence was estimated in 86% for women in reproductive age and also in hematopoietic stem cell and solid organ donors ¹⁷.

HCMV congenital infection is caused due to the mother-to-child virus transmission. The highest risk of transmission (~50%) is associated with pregnant woman with a primary infection, while the risk is lower (~ 2%) for cases of reinfection or reactivation¹⁶. However, due to the high seroprevalence of the virus in the population, the majority of the congenital cases happen due to reinfection or virus reactivation¹⁸.

HCMV establish benign infection in immunocompetent host with minor symptoms or in some cases, with symptoms similar to mononucleosis infection^{2,19}. However, HCMV causes serious infections in immunocompromised individuals due to the immature or immunosuppressed immune system. In the cases of HIV-infected patients, the most usual manifestation of HCMV infection is retinitis. It is characterised by a retinal haemorrhagic necrosis. The use of antiretroviral therapies in HIV+ patients has decreased the incidence of HCMV².

In the case of solid organ transplant (SOT) recipients, HCMV is associated with high rate of morbidity and mortality. The risk of HCMV infection after transplantation depends on the serostatus of both the donor and the recipient before the transplant, as well as the type of organ to be transplanted. HCMV infection in SOT recipients causes viral syndrome which includes fever, neutropenia, leukopenia or hepatosplenomegaly. In Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplant (HSCT) patients, the principal manifestation is pneumonia^{2,19}.

Congenital infection is produced by a primary infection or a reactivation of the virus in the mother during the pregnancy^{2,19} or after the birth due to the breastfeeding¹². Between 10-15% of the child shows symptoms after the birth, in addition to a delay in the intrauterine growth. Mortality in symptomatic children is about 30% and survivors present neurologic, visual and hearing sequelae. In asymptomatic children, between 10-17% of them develop hearing and neurologic effects^{2,19}.

Immune response against HCMV

Innate response

Innate immunity plays an important role in the immune response against HCMV. The virus stimulates the TLR (Toll-Like Receptors) which activates different pathways that leads to inflammatory cytokine secretion. Cytokines recruit different cells of the immune system such as the NK cells^{2,20} that are involved in virus clearance. NK cells express receptors that recognize and eliminate the infected cells^{2,20,21}.

Humoral response

The role of HCMV-specific antibodies is not still fully understood. Some studies have shown that antibodies are able to reduce the severity of the illness by decreasing the viral load. After infection, antibodies against many HCMV proteins are found: tegument proteins such as pp65 and pp150, envelope glycoproteins such as gB and gH and proteins involved in transcription such as IE-1 can be detected in the blood. In the majority of infected individuals, antibodies against gB can be found, 50% of which are neutralizing antibodies^{20,22}.

Cellular response

Cellular response mediated by cytotoxic TCD8+ cells and helper TCD4+ cells plays an important role in the resolution of the primary infection. Moreover, the high presence of TCD4+ and TCD8+ cells allows to control HCMV reactivation since they repress replication during latency^{20,21}. Most of the studies have shown HCMV-specific CD4+ and CD8+ T-cells in response to stimulation with proteins pp65 and IE-1, gB, pUL86, pp28, IE-2, pUL36, pUL48, pp10, pUL113 and IRS-1^{20,22,23}.

Treatments and Vaccines for HCMV

Antiviral drugs are currently used for treating HCMV infection. In transplant patients, intravenous ganciclovir and oral valganciclovir are considered as a first-line treatment, while Foscarnet and cidofovir are used as second-line in cases of first line treatment failure²⁴. Although during the last years treatments have improved, they have different disadvantages such as toxicity and the selection of resistance mutations after long period of treatment. Foscarnet is usually used when Ganciclovir/valganciclovir therapy fails, and also for patients who are intolerant or resistant to these drugs. Cidofovir, however, is usually used for VIH+ patients²⁵. During pregnancy, neither cidofovir and Foscarnet are recommended since they are teratogenic agents²⁶. On the other hand, valacyclovir seems to reduce vertical transmission and could also be effective as therapy for congenital infection during pregnancy, according with some studies²⁷. Moreover, ganciclovir and valganciclovir have been used for congenital HCMV infection in neonates²⁸.

In 1999, the Institute of Medicine in United States designated the development of a vaccine against HCMV as a high priority²⁹. Different vaccine attempts have been developed in the last fifty years, although none of them met the criteria to be commercialized. Living vaccine attempts have been developed using AD169 and Towne attenuated strains, as well as vector and replicon particle vaccines. Non-living vaccines development attempts include DNA or RNA-

based, dense body, virus like particles and peptide vaccines ³⁰. Both cellular and humoral response are important in the prevention of the infection. Latest studies have pointed out that neutralizing antibodies, may be key for protection against HCMV ^{31,32}. Different approximation using gB and the pentameric complex have been developed, since there seems to elicit a strong neutralizing antibody response ³³. Moreover, some studies also suggest a neutralizing antibody response against the complex gM/gN, which may be potential candidate for vaccine development ³⁴. However, most of these studies show partial neutralizing protection, suggesting that other proteins may be also involved in entry during HCMV infection of different cell types.

Bacterial Artificial Chromosomes (BACs) in HCMV studies

Bacterial Artificial Chromosomes (BAC) are plasmids that can be stably maintained in *E. coli* bacteria and can carry large DNA fragments, higher than 300 kb. For this reason, they have been widely used for HCMV studies, since it allows easy modifications of the viral sequence and its functional studies by its expression in eukaryotic cells ^{35,36}. Different strategies can be followed to include the genome in a BAC, such as the homologous recombination of the viral genome with the BAC sequences³⁵. In the present work, BAC BADrUL131-Y4 was used. It contains a Kanamycin resistance gene flanked by TR sequences, and the repaired version of the gene UL131 because the laboratory AD169 presents a non-functional version of this gene ³⁷.

AIM OF WORK

The main objective of this work was the development and improvement of a molecular method to generate mutants of HCMV that allows the propagation of the viral progeny to study the effect of the mutation. In order to achieve this, a protocol based on a method described by Wanner and Datsenko (2000), in which specific HCMV genes are replaced by a Kanamycin resistance was applied and optimised (Figure 5). Mutant viruses were expressed in MRC-5 and HEK 293T in order to produce the WT and mutant progenies. This methodology is a powerful technique for generating mutants in order to analyse the impact of each target gene which can be used to design and develop better treatments and vaccines against HCMV.

Figure 5. Homologous recombination based on the technique described by Wanner and Datsenko. A specific gene is replaced by a cassette constructed with the antibiotic resistance gene and homologous tails to the beginning and the end of the gene to delete. The antibiotic resistance gene chosen was Kanamycin resistance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Strains and media

Escherichia coli strain DH5 α λ pir containing HCMV BADrUL131-Y4 BAC was used for both homologous recombination development. It was kindly provided by Dr. Peter Shenk of Princeton University. Strain λ pir is crucial since the helper plasmid for recombineering (pKD46) has conditional (oriRy) replicons that require the trans-acting II protein (the pir gene product) for replication. Plasmid pKD4 containing the Kanamycin resistance (Kan^R) and plasmid pKD46 containing the Ampicillin resistance were used. pKD46 was used for homologous recombination as a helper plasmid since it contains Exo, β and γ genes, expressed by the arabinose inducible promoter³⁸. It was used Arabinose 1M (Sigma) to induce the expression of the RED genes. BADrUL131-Y4 derives from ad169 cytomegalovirus strain where UL131 sequence was repaired and contains a Chloramphenicol resistance gene³⁷. Antibiotic resistant selection was done in LB media or LB agar media (Conda) with Ampicillin 100 μ g/mL (A0166-5G, Sigma), Kanamycin 50 μ g/mL (ThermoFisher) and Chloramphenicol 34 μ g/mL (C0378-5G, Sigma). S.O.C media (Invitrogen) was used after the electroporation of the cells.

Construction of the parental strain: Transformation of *E. coli* DH5 α carrying the BAC with pKD46

Transformation was performed by electroporation based on the protocol described by Hollenback, Lyman and Cheng³⁹. *E. coli* DH5 α λ pir containing the BACbone were streaked in a LB plate with 34 μ g/mL chloramphenicol and incubated at 37°C overnight. One colony of the culture was inoculated in 5 mL LB with 34 μ g/mL chloramphenicol and incubated at 37°C 150 rpm overnight. The day after, the appropriate volume of o/n culture was used to reach an OD₆₀₀ of 0.1 on 25 mL of LB-Chloramphenicol. The culture was incubated at 37°C 150 rpm to achieve an OD₆₀₀ about 1.3 (approximately 3 hours). After that, the culture was set on ice for 20 minutes to cool down the cells. Further steps were carried out at 4°C, including centrifugations. 5 mL of the cell culture was pelleted at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes to remove the LB media, and resuspended in 2 mL of cold Hypure water (Gybo). Cells were washed three times in order to make electrocompetent cells. Cells were resuspended three times in 2 mL, 1 mL and 500 μ L of Hypure water successively. Between washed cells were centrifugated at 13000 rpm for 2 minutes and supernatants were carefully discarded. After the last wash, cells were resuspended in 50 μ L of cold Hypure water and 50 ng of pKD46 plasmid were added to the cells. The mixture was incubated on ice for 5 minutes. Electroporation was performed by adding the cells with pKD46 plasmid on a pre-chilled 1mm electroporation cuvette. Electroporation was performed

by using the BioRad Gene pulser. Optimal conditions were 1.8 KW and 5 ms. Immediately after electroporation, 900 μ L of S.O.C media was added to the cells and were incubated 2 hours at 37°C with no agitation. After this time, 100 μ L of the bacterial suspension were plated on a LB plate with 100 μ g/mL Ampicillin and 34 μ g/mL Chloramphenicol and incubated at 30°C overnight because pKD46 is a suicide plasmid at temperatures above 37°C. For storage at -80°C, 900 μ L of cell culture were inoculated in a cryotube with the appropriate volume (20%) of glycerol 100%.

Design of the Kanamycin resistant (Kan^R) cassette

The design of the appropriate cassette that will be used to replace the deleted target gene is a crucial step in the homologous recombination process. The constructed cassette contains the Kanamycin resistance gene flanked by two homologous sequences to the selected gene⁴⁰. Oligonucleotides to amplify the Kan^R cassette included specific sequences of 17 and 18 bp, respectively of the 5' and 3' ends of the cassette and in the 5' end of each primer a 50-bp tails homologous to the sequence flanking the gene selected to be deleted (Table 1). Oligonucleotides were designed by using the sequence of the Ad169 Cytomegalovirus strain (X17403.1). Both oligonucleotides had a T_m of 55°C. Following the method developed by Datsenko and Wanner³⁸, the kanamycin resistance gene (Kan^R) was amplified from pKD4, which contains the Kan^R gene flanked by two FRT sequences. pKD4 plasmid was extracted from *E. coli* by using the NZYMiniprep Kit (Nzytech). Target gene for deletion were those 20 that code for proteins predicted to be putative membrane proteins that may be involved in viral entry and may be potential targets for neutralizing antibodies⁴¹. In addition, other well-known proteins such as pp65, IE-1, gO and gM were deleted by this method.

PCR amplification of the cassette was performed using EconoTaq[®] PLUS (Lucigen). Following PCR, the 1724-bp PCR product was gel purified (GelPure, NzyTech) in order to electroporate the cells.

Table 1. Oligonucleotides used for amplification of the knockout cassette. The sequence with homology to the Kan^R cassette from the plasmid pKD4 is underlined. The remainder of the oligonucleotide sequence is homologous to the flanking region of the deleted ORF. Positive control oligonucleotides are marked with an asterisk (*). TM 55°C for each oligonucleotide.

Oligonucleotide	Sequence (5'→3')
C(+)-F*	ATGGAGCCCACGCCGATGCTCCGCGACCGGGATCACGACGACGCGCCCC <u>GCATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
C(+)-R*	TTATCCCGATGTTGACACCGTCCCGGTTGTATTGGAATTGTCCCGGTTAATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL2Kan ^R -F	ATGGCCGAAGACTCGGTGCGGATCCTTATAGTCGAAGATGACAACGACGCG <u>GCATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL2Kan ^R -R	TTATAAAAGAGCGTCTCGAAGCAGCTTGAGCCACACTACGGTCCAGATGATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL5Kan ^R -F	ATGTTTCTAGGCTACTCTGACTGTGTAGATCCCGGCCTTGCTGTGTATCGG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL5Kan ^R -R	CTACACGGTAGCGACGAGACGTTGATAGCGGTATTTAGAGGACGGGCGATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL6Kan ^R -F	ATGCATGCTAAGATGAACGGGTGGGCTGGGGTGGCGCTTGGA <u>ACTCACTGGCATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL6Kan ^R -R	CTACATTAACAAACCACGTTCTTCATCGTCCACGTGGCTTCGCCAGCGTCTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL7Kan ^R -F	ATGGCTCCGACGTGAGCTCCCATCTTCTAACGGTTACACAATCCCGTTGG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL7Kan ^R -R	CTATAACTTTGGTTTACTACATAACAACCTCCACCATCCATAATACAAATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL8Kan ^R -F	ATGACTAACCTGGGCTATATGCATCGGAAAATTATAACGGAAAATTATGAG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL8Kan ^R -R	TCACAGCTCCGTGTCCGTCATAAATACTGTCCGTAAGTTTATTGCTTTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL9Kan ^R -F	ATGTATAGATACACGTGGCTGCTTTGGTGGATAACAATATTGCTTCGATG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL9Kan ^R -R	TTAAGCGGCGGTGAGCATACTGTTGTATCGGTATTGTGAATTTATTCCTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US7Kan ^R -F	ATGCGGATCCAGCTGCTTCTGGTAGCTACCTGGTGGCGTCTATCGTCGCG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US7Kan ^R -R	TTAGCCCTTGACAGGATAGGTCAAAGATTATATGTAGTTTTCCGGTAATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US9Kan ^R -F	ATGATCCTGTGGTCCCGTCCACCTGTTCTTCTTCTGGCACTGGTGTCTG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US9Kan ^R -R	TCAATCGTCTTTAGCCTCTTCTTCCCGTGAGGTCCTTCCGGTGGCGCGGTTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US13Kan ^R -F	ATGGACCCCGCTACCGTCGCTACATTGCCGCAATGGGCTTCCCTCCTG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US13Kan ^R -R	CTACGAGCCACCGCCACCTTCGCAATACGAGGATCTGAAGGCGGCAAAGATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US14Kan ^R -F	ATGGAGACAGTTTCCACGCAGCGGAAACCGCGTCGTCGAAACGGAGCGGC <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US14Kan ^R -R	TCAGGCAGCCTTGTCTGGAACGTCGAGTGGTGGTGTGAGGATGACGCTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US16Kan ^R -F	ATGGGTCTGCGCTTTCCACCGCGACCCAGCGACAGATCGTGTTTCGGCGG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US16Kan ^R -R	CTAGGGCGAGAGGGTGGACAACGGCGTCGACGACGAAGCATGGGACAGGTTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US17Kan ^R -F	ATGTCTCCGAACCTAGAGGCCACCGGACGGCTGGGCGCCCCACCCCGC <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US17Kan ^R -R	TTACGCCATGGTTCGCGTGAGGTTTCTGTACTCCCGCAAAGGTCACTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US18Kan ^R -F	ATGGGCGACACCGCCTCGGTTTCCGAACACCATGAGTCGCCGACGGTCACG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US18Kan ^R -R	TTACAACAAGCTGAGGAGACTCACCGCTCGATGCGTCCGCCGTGTTCTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US20Kan ^R -F	ATGCAGGCGCAGGAGGCTAACGCGCTGCTGCTCTCCCGCATGGAGGCTCTG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US20Kan ^R -R	TTAGGACTTCCCGTCTACTGGCGGCTGTCAAAGTCCCGTTGTCCAAAGTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US21Kan ^R -F	ATGTCGCTCCGCGGTCAGGTCCAGATAGCCCGTGGTCTTCTGCTGCGG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US21Kan ^R -R	TTAGGAGACGAACTGGGGCGACCCGCTGCTGTGGCAGCGACCGTCGCTTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
US30Kan ^R -F	ATGGGGAACCCCGGAGCCCGCTCGATCGACGGCTACGGTTCAGGAATGTG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
US30Kan ^R -R	TTATACAGGCGGAAACACAGACGAATACTCGGGGGCTGCGAGGGAACCGTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL42Kan ^R -F	ATGGAGCCCACGCCGATGCTCCGCGACCGGGATCACGACGACGCGCCCC <u>GCATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL42Kan ^R -R	TTATCCCGATGTTGACACCGTCCCGGTTGTATTGGAATTGTCCCGGTTAATAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG
UL44Kan ^R -F	ATGGATCGCAAGACGCGCCTCTCGGAGCCCGACGCTGGCGCTGCGGCTG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL44Kan ^R -R	CTAGCCGCACTTTTGCTTCTTGGTGTAGGGACGAACTCGAACGTTACAGTAAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG

Table 1 (continued). Oligonucleotides used for amplification of the knockout cassette. The sequence with homology to the kan^R cassette from the plasmid pKD4 is underlined. The remainder of the oligonucleotide sequence is homologous to the flanking region of the deleted ORF. Positive control oligonucleotide are marked with an (*). TM 55°C for each oligonucleotide.

Oligonucleotide	Sequence (5'→3')
UL121Kan ^R -F	ATGTGGGGGTGCGGGTGGTCCCGGATAATTGTCCTTCTCCCCCTCATGTGG <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
UL121Kan ^R -R	CTCCACAGGGCCGCCGACGATGCTGAACGACAGGATCAGACAGACGGT <u>AAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG</u>
pp65Kan ^R -F	ATGTCTCAGGCATCGTCCTCGCCCGGTGAGGGACCCTCGTCGGAAGCGGC <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
pp65Kan ^R -R	CTAGATGCGGGTGCAGTGCCTGCGGGTGGTGGAAAGTGGAAAGCGGTGCTGAT <u>AAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG</u>
IE1Kan ^R -F	ATGGAGTCTCTGCCAAGAGAAAGATGGACCCTGATAATCCTGACGAGGGGC <u>CATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
IE1Kan ^R -R	TTACTGGTCAGCCTTGCTTCTAGTCCATAGGGTGGTGGTCTTGCCTCTA <u>AAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG</u>
gOKan ^R -F	ATGGGGAGAAAAGAGATGATGGTGAGAGACGTCCCTAAGATGGTGTCTT <u>GCATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
gOKan ^R -R	GGGCTGTAAATCTGTCCACCCTCAATAGCCTTTGGTGGTGGTGCAGTA <u>AAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG</u>
gMKan ^R -F	ATGGCCCCCTGCACGTGGATAAGGTGAATACACGGACATGGAGCGCTT <u>GCATTACACGTCTTGAG</u>
gMKan ^R -R	TTAAGCGTCCTCGAAGTCTTCATCATCGTCGTCCTCTTCTCGCGGAT <u>AAGGTTTAACGGTTGTG</u>

Transformation of *E. coli* DH5α λpir+BAC+pKD46 strain with Kan^R cassette

Transformation of parental strain with the specific Kan^R cassettes was performed by electroporation using the protocol described by Hollenback, Lyman and Cheng³⁹. Parental strain was streaked in a LB plate with 34 µg/mL chloramphenicol and 100 µg/mL ampicillin and incubated at 30°C overnight. One colony of the culture was inoculated in 5 mL LB with 34 µg/mL chloramphenicol and 100 µg/mL Ampicillin and incubated at 30°C and 150 rpm overnight. The day after, the appropriate volume of culture was used to reach an OD₆₀₀ of 0.1 in 100 mL of LB with 34 µg/mL chloramphenicol and 100 µg/mL Ampicillin and was incubated at 30°C 150 rpm at 37°C to achieve an OD₆₀₀ of 0,4 (approximately 3 hours, acceptable OD₆₀₀ range 0.30-0.50). After incubation, 1 mL of 1M Arabinose was added in order to induce pKD46 β, γ and exo genes. Cell culture with arabinose was incubated at 37°C 150rpm until reaching an OD₆₀₀ 1.2 (approximately one-hour, acceptable OD₆₀₀ range 1-1.3). After this step the culture was left on ice during 20 minutes. Further steps were carried out at 4°C, including the centrifugations. 50 mL of pre-chilled cell culture was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes to remove the LB media. Cells were washed five times with cold water to make the cells electrocompetent. Five successive washes using 30 mL, 10 mL, 2 mL, 1 mL and 500 µL of Hypure water were performed. Between washes cells were centrifuged at 13000 g 2 minutes and the supernatants were removed carefully. Cells were resuspended in 300 µL of cold Hypure water, and culture was distributed on three different pre-chilled 1.5 mL tubes (100 µL in each). 200-250 ng of each Kan^R cassette were added to the cells, and the mixture was incubated 5 minutes on ice. Electroporation was performed by adding the cells with the Kan^R cassette on a pre-chilled 1mm

electroporation cuvette. Electroporation was performed by using BioRad Gene pulser. Optimal conditions were 1.8 KW and 5 ms. Immediately after electroporation, 500 μ L of S.O.C media (Invitrogen) were added to the cells and were incubated for 2 hours at 37°C with no agitation. After incubation, 100 μ L of the bacterial suspension were plated on a LB plate with 50 μ g/mL Kanamycin and incubated at 37°C overnight and after that period an additional incubation between 24-48 hours at room temperature.

Deletion verification

In order to verify whether the Kan^R cassette insertion was located in the correct place, two testing procedures were performed. First verification was based on the different size of the mutant when the Kan^R gene is integrated and the WT gene. Second verification was based in the fragment amplified using a combination of internal oligonucleotides of the Kan^R gene with the external oligonucleotides of each of the target genes (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Deletion verification (A) by size and (B) by internal oligonucleotides

The verification was performed using a colony PCR with designed testing oligonucleotides (Table 2a). Testing oligonucleotides are homologous to the upstream and downstream sequences of the deleted ORF.

For colony PCR, a colony grown under Kanamycin selection was added to 20 µl of NaOH 20 mM. The mixture was heated at 95°C for 5 minutes and then centrifugated at 13000 rpm for 1 minute. 1 µl of the supernatant was used for PCR amplification. Amplified products were separated by electrophoresis to check the size of the amplified bands.

The verification by using internal Kan^R oligonucleotide was also performed by a colony PCR, as previously described using oligonucleotides described in Table 2b.

In the case of the WT and the mutant amplicon were similar in size, and a digestion analysis was performed in order to distinguish the positive colonies. For this analysis, a digestion reaction containing 3 µl of the PCR product, 1µL of FastDigest Buffer, 1 µl of *KpnI* and 5 µl of H₂O was made and incubated for 5 minutes at 37°C

Table 2. Oligonucleotides used for mutant validation. TM 55°C for each one

^a Oligonucleotides used to check the correct insertion of the deletion cassette

^b Oligonucleotides used for a second check whose sequence is a part of the Kan^R gene

Oligonucleotide	Sequence (5'→3')
UL2Kan ^R cp-F ^a	GTGCCTATTTCACTCTTC
UL2Kan ^R cp-R ^a	GTATCGGCATACAATGTG
UL5Kan ^R cp-F ^a	TCCAGGGCAACTATAAC
UL5Kan ^R cp-R ^a	ATTCAAACAGTGAGTTACC
UL6Kan ^R cp-F ^a	TCCATCTGTCGTTTCTG
UL6Kan ^R cp-R ^a	CCTCTCCACGTTTGTA
UL7Kan ^R cp-F ^a	GACGTTATCCAAGAACATAA
UL7Kan ^R cp-R ^a	GTGGAGTAACCGTAGTC
UL8Kan ^R cp-F ^a	GTTTAGCACCACAACACTAC
UL8Kan ^R cp-R ^a	CTGGCTTGCTATCTATTT
UL9Kan ^R cp-F ^a	CTACGGTTACTCCACAA
UL9Kan ^R cp-R ^a	GTAAGTGGATCACCTACT
US7Kan ^R cp-F ^a	CTTATGTTGATCCGTGTG
US7Kan ^R cp-R ^a	GATAGGTGTGACGATGT

Table 2 (continued). Oligonucleotides used for mutant validation. TM 55°C for each one^a Oligonucleotides used to check the correct insertion of the deletion cassette^b Oligonucleotides used for a second check whose sequence is a part of the Kan^R gene

Oligonucleotide	Sequence (5'→3')
US9Kan ^R cp-F ^a	GATCCGAGAAATGGTATG
US9Kan ^R cp-R ^a	TTCGTCCTCCCTATAGTA
US13Kan ^R cp-F ^a	GGCACCTATCATCATTAC
US13Kan ^R cp-R ^a	GGGTGTCTTCATCTTTG
US14Kan ^R cp-F ^a	AGATCGTCTTGCCTTC
US14Kan ^R cp-R ^a	TGTGAAAGACCACTAGG
US16Kan ^R cp-F ^a	CTATGAGAACCTGGTGTA
US16KanRcp-R ^a	GACGAGAATGGTGAAAC
US17KanRcp-F ^a	CTAGAGACAGACGATGAA
US17KanRcp-R ^a	GGAGATTTGGAAGAGGA
US18KanRcp-F ^a	CCTGTCA GTTCTTTCC
US18KanRcp-R ^a	TCTGATTCGGAGACAT
US20KanRcp-F ^a	CACGACATCGAGTATGA
US20KanRcp-R ^a	GAGGCTGAGATGAGAAA
US21KanRcp-F ^a	AAGCAGATTCCTTTCC
US21KanRcp-R ^a	GGTGAGAAAGAAGCTGTA
US30KanRcp-F ^a	CCTGAGCAACTGTTATC
US30KanRcp-R ^a	GAGGAACCCGAGGAATA
UL42KanRcp-F ^a	GGGTTCTTGCGTTCTG
UL42KanRcp-R ^a	CAAACCACGCCGATCAT
UL44KanRcp-F ^a	CGTGTGTGCTCTATAA
UL44KanRcp-R ^a	GTAACAGGTCGCAGTAG
UL121KanRcp-F ^a	GAGGAACAAGTCTCAGT
UL121KanRcp-R ^a	TAGTCAAGTTAGTGCATTG
pp65KanRcp-F ^a	CACCGCTGTATATTTG
pp65KanRcp-R ^a	CACCGTGATACCCTAAT
IE1KanRcp-F ^a	GGTAGGGTATGTGTCTG
IE1KanRcp-R ^a	GAGTAGGATTACAGAGTATAAC
gOKanRcp-F ^a	TGGGTCTGGTTACATATC
gOKanRcp-R ^a	CGACA ACTAGCACTAAAC
gMKanRcp-F ^a	GCTCCCATCGTAGTATT
gMKanRcp-R ^a	GTTTCTCCGTGTGTATATTA
KanRInt-F ^b	GGATCTCCTGTCATCTC
KanRInt-R ^b	CATGATATTCGCAAGC

Table 3. Size (bp) of each fragment for the deletion test
 First and second columns: size with specific oligonucleotides for each gene
 Third and fourth columns: size with specific and internal kanamycin oligonucleotides

ORF	Specific oligonucleotides		Specific and Kanamycin oligonucleotides	
	Wild Type	Kan ^R mutant	Internal primer-Specific F	Internal primer-Specific R
UL2	520	1961	1067	1285
UL5	928	2151	1079	1363
UL6	1342	2211	1226	1276
UL7	1114	2169	1141	1319
UL8	831	2186	1206	1291
UL9	1157	2194	1179	1306
UL42	779	2128	1233	1351
UL44	1903	2325	1454	1162
UL121	893	2125	1179	1237
US7	1030	2081	1070	1302
US9	1192	2172	1050	1413
US13	1150	2668	1130	1249
US14	1387	2178	1119	1350
US16	1549	2343	1425	1209
US17	1410	2252	1239	1304
US18	1362	2261	1208	1344
US20	1319	2278	1189	1380
US21	1242	2246	1270	1267
US30	1974	2648	1179	1306
pp65	1905	1949	1044	1196
IE1	2132	2096	1018	1369
gO	1796	2119	1131	1279
gM	1410	2015	1126	1180

Viral production by transfection in HEK 293T and MRC-5 cells

The WT virus (positive control) and the recombinant deletion mutant viruses were produced by transfecting HEK 293T and MRC-5 cells with the corresponding BACbones. DNA preparations of the WT BAC and mutants BACs were extracted from transformed *E. coli* using the Macherey-Nagel™ NucleoBond™ BAC 100 Kit. Preparations of the different HCMV BACbones were used for transfection of the cells using Lipofectamine 2000 (Invitrogen). Virus progeny of the transfected cells were followed by fluorescence foci and evidence of cytopathic effect.

Briefly, the day before seed 500.000 cells/well in a 6-well plate. Next day confluency must be approximately 80-90%. 4 µg of each BAC were inoculated in 50 µL of DMEM with no serum and gently mixed. 12 µL of Lipofectamine 2000 were diluted in 50 µL DMEM without serum and incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature. After the 5-minute incubation, DNA and Lipofectamine 2000 dilutions were combined and incubated for 20 minutes at room temperature. 100 µL of complexes were added to each well containing cells and medium and gently mixed by rocking the plate. Cells were incubated at 37°C in a CO₂ incubator for 18-48 hours prior to see GFP expression. Medium was changed after 4 hours. Cells were subjected to three rounds of freezing and thawing to prepare viral lysates. Fluorescent cells were visualized in a confocal SP5 Leica microscope.

To demonstrate the formation of mutant viral progeny, WT and mutant viral lysates were used to infect freshly seeded 90% confluent MRC-5 cells. Viral infection was monitored by detection of GFP expression and cytopathic effect.

RESULTS

Selection of candidate genes for deletion, oligonucleotides and recombinant HCMV generation

We selected 20 genes with predicted transmembrane domain and with unknown function. In addition, another set of known genes involved in viral entry (UL44, IE-1, pp65, gM, gB and gO). Genes that were deleted from HCMV genome and their specific oligonucleotides are listed in table 4. After purification of the Kan cassette, 50-60 µg/mL was considered optimal concentration for transformation, avoiding impurities in the electroporation step (Table 4, first column).

Recombinant viruses were generated by substituting each of the target genes with the pre-constructed Kan^R cassette. To do so, pKD46 was transformed into an *E. coli* DH5α λpir containing the WT BAC and positive colonies were selected in LB+Amp+Chl plates. Several attempts were required to optimize the protocol to obtain the parental strain. Optimal electroporation constants were 1.8 kW and 3.8 ms. Although the time constant differed from the optimal (5 ms), several colonies were obtained after 72 hours of incubation at room temperature (Table 4, fourth and fifth columns). Using the parental strain, Kan^R cassette to delete each specific gene was transformed into the parental strain following the protocol described in section 4 of “materials and methods” and selected in LB+Kan plates.

For this step, it was important to assure an appropriate number of competent cells for the transformation since growth and arabinose induction are done in two different steps. The first step is a 3-hours incubation were cells have an exponential growth to achieve an OD₆₀₀ of 0.3-0.5; and the second is a 1-hour incubation after Arabinose addition obtaining an OD₆₀₀ of 1-1.3. Both OD₆₀₀ range and electroporation conditions were optimal, and colonies were obtained after the first attempt for the majority of mutants. Electroporation conditions are collected in table 4.

Table 4. Parameters required during the transformation step: concentration of each cassette after purification ($\mu\text{g/mL}$); OD_{600} of the cells after 3 hours of incubation and after arabinose induction in case of transformation with the Kan^R cassettes; Electroporation parameters in KW and ms.

Cassette	Cassette concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	OD_{600} (3h incubation)	OD_{600} (after Arabinose induction)	V (KW)	Time constant (ms)
pKD46	5.1	1.1	No arabinose induction	1.8	3.8
Kan ^R -UL2	66.8	0.45	1	1.8	5.1
Kan ^R -UL5	71.8	0.5	1.1	1.8	4.9
Kan ^R -UL6	68.5	0.45	1.2	1.8	5.1
Kan ^R -UL7	119	0.45	1.2	1.8	5
Kan ^R -UL8	149.6	0.45	1.2	1.8	5.2
Kan ^R -UL9	84.3	0.45	1	1.8	5
Kan ^R -UL42	66.6	0.45	1.2	1.8	5.1
Kan ^R -UL44	88.7	0.4	1	1.8	4.9
Kan ^R -UL121	99.3	0.45	1.2	1.8	5.1
Kan ^R -US7	49	0.45	1.2	1.8	5
Kan ^R -US9	48.7	0.38	0.94	1.8	5.3
Kan ^R -US13	114.4	0.38	0.94	1.8	5.3
Kan ^R -US14	37*	0.5	1,1	1.8	4.7
Kan ^R -US16	84,5	0.4	1	1.8	5.1
Kan ^R -US17	119.8	0.35	0.9	1.8	5.3
Kan ^R -US18	127.1	0.38	0.94	1.8	5.4
Kan ^R -US20	112	0.42	0.94	1.8	4.5
Kan ^R -US21	116	0.42	0.94	1.8	4
Kan ^R -US30	165.5	0.42	0.94	1.8	4.2
Kan ^R -pp65	123.6	0.419	0.9	1.8	4.2
Kan ^R -IE1	96.7	0.419	0.9	1.8	4.2
Kan ^R -gO	107.8	0.419	0.9	1.8	4.3
Kan ^R -gM	128.3	0.419	0.9	1.8	4.3

Recombinant HCMV verification

BAC DNA was isolated from the bacteria colonies obtained in kanamycin plates and analysed by PCR in order to test the correct integration of the antibiotic cassette within the ORF of the deleted gene. PCR was performed by using oligonucleotides homologous to a specific region 5' and 3' up- and downstream of the deleted gene (**a** and **b**), and also oligonucleotides homologous to the internal sequence of Kan^R gene (**c** and **d**). A schematic representation of the oligonucleotides location is shown in Figure 7. Oligonucleotides sequences are listed in table 2a.

Size (bp) of both WT and mutant amplicons of each gene have been predicted by using the HCMV sequence Ad169, and are shown in table 3 in order to distinguish between them.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the oligonucleotides location for each target gene tested.

Figure 8 shows some examples of gene verification results. Each of the panels correspond to one of the deleted gene using homologous recombination. Different number of colonies was tested in each case, depending on the number of colonies obtained in the selective plates after transformation. Moreover, percentage of positives clones obtained differed for each deleted gene, ranging from 1.8% to 100%. In general, the percentage of positive clones obtained was over 10%. Only in some cases such as with UL9, UL121, US30 and IE-1, the percentages were lower, obtaining a 1.8%, 4.2%, 6.7% and 6.7% respectively (Table 5). No mutants were obtained only with UL42 deletion. The explanation for this could be that the gene sequence used for designing the oligonucleotides does not start with the starting codon (ATG), which could indicate that the available sequence of this gene is not correct. The average of positive colonies for all the tested genes was 30.2%. Data of tested colonies and proportion of positive and negative colonies are shown in Table 5 and figure 9. Results of the amplified products can be observed showing different fragment sizes obtained for the WT versus the deletion mutant.

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

H

I

J

K

L

Figure 8. 1% agarose gel showing the different amplicons obtained in the validation test for each gene deletion. (A) UL2; (B) UL5; (C) UL6; (D) UL7; (E) UL8; (F) UL42; (G) UL44; (H) UL121; (I) US7; (J) US9; (K) US13; (L) US14; (M) US18; (N) US16. The first lane or each gel is the band corresponding with the wild type BAC (WT), mutant BAC (Δ) and the third and fourth lanes are the combinations between the specific (a, b) and the Kanamycin internal oligonucleotides (c, d).

Table 5. Number of colonies tested for each target. It shows the number of positive colonies for the first and second testing and also the percentage of positive for each gene deletion.

Deleted gene	Colonies tested	Number of positive (1 ^o testing)	Number of positive (2 ^o testing)	Percentage of positive
UL2	20	4	4	20%
UL5	4	1	1	25%
UL6	7	1	1	14.3%
UL7	4	2	2	50%
UL8	16	2	14	12.5%
UL9	24	1	1	4.2%
UL42	28	0	0	0%
UL44	19	2	2	10.5%
UL121	55	1	1	1.8%
US7	10	6	6	60%
US9	42	21	21	50%
US13	10	1	1	10%
US14	4	3	3	75%
US16	10	5	5	50%
US17	4	3	3	75%
US18	22	6	6	27.2%
US18 (second copy)	14	9	-	64.3%
US20	15	11	11	73.3%
US21	15	7	7	46.7%
US30	15	1	1	6.7%
pp65	15	3	3	20%
IE1	15	1	1	6.7%
gO	15	7	7	46.7%
gM	6	6	6	100%

For some genes (UL44, UL121, US7, US14 and US18) (Figure 8G, H, I, L, M) amplified products were observed in both WT and mutant in the same positive colony. One possible explanation is that two colonies (one containing a WT BAC and other one containing a mutant BAC) were dragged at the same time for the testing, obtaining an amplification of both WT and mutant BACs. The second more feasible explanation is that the BAC contained more than one copy of the specific gene to be deleted and only one copy of the gene was deleted remaining also the WT amplicon. In order to elucidate whether the second hypothesis was real, a re-transformation of the positive colony with the Kan^R cassette was tried. However, since bacteria

already contained the Kan^R gene, a lawn covering the whole plate was obtained. Isolated colonies were obtained and tested by a PCR, obtaining only one band in each lane (Figure 10). This result confirmed that in the case of US18 the BAC contained two copies of the gene. Number of positive colonies can be observed in Table 5 and Figure 9.

Figure 9. Proportion of positive and negative colonies from the total obtained for each gene deletion, according to the data collected in table 5. Positive colonies are shown in green and negative colonies are shown in blue. US18* indicates colonies positives and negatives obtained for the re-transformation of cells with a pre-obtained Δ US18-HCMV positive in order to delete the second US18 gene.

Figure 10. Δ US18-HCMV positive colonies. (A) Colonies obtained during first transformation, in which two bands (marked with an arrow) were observed in the positive ones; (B) Colonies obtained during the second transformation in which only one band is observed in each lane.

In case of Δ pp65-HCMV the mutant and WT amplicons were similar in size to be distinguished thus, digestion analysis was performed and results are shown in Figure 11. 3 of the 15 samples were not digested by *KpnI*, showing that these 3 samples are Δ pp65-HCMV positive. For IE-1 this method could not be used since no enzymes that only cut the Kan^R fragment were available. For these reason, Δ IE1-HCMV were confirmed with a PCR by using internal Kan^R oligonucleotides.

Figure 11. Enzymatic restriction assay for Δ pp65-HCMV testing by using *KpnI*. One band in the lane indicates a Δ pp65-HCMV positive (marked with an arrow), while two bands indicate a WT BAC.

Transformation of UL8-Kan^R cassette by using frozen electrocompetent *E. coli* cells for the electroporation

Most protocols available recommend to use freshly prepared electrocompetent cells for higher efficiency of the recombination events. However, to facilitate the quick transformation of the method we also optimized transformation efficiency with frozen electrocompetent *E. coli* comparable to the transformation performed with fresh electrocompetent cells. UL8-Kan^R cassette was used as an example for this experiment. Electroporation parameters were similar using both electrocompetent cells (Table 6). 20 out of 190 colonies were tested in the case of the transformation with frozen cells, while all 16 obtained colonies were tested in case of transformation with fresh-made cells (Table 6). In the case of electroporation with frozen *E. coli*, 13 of 20 (65%) colonies were Δ UL8-HCMV positive, while only two colonies were Δ UL8-HCMV positive for the transformation with fresh cells (12.5%; Table 6). This result showed a higher recombination efficiency in the case of electroporation with frozen cells but also a greater transformation efficiency if we take into account the huge number of obtained colonies.

Table 6. Electroporation parameters and number of colonies obtained between transformation of UL8-KanR cassette by using frozen and fresh electrocompetent cells.

	V (KW)	Time (ms)	Number of obtained colonies	Number of colonies tested	Number of positive colonies
Frozen cells	1.8	4.7	190	20	13
Fresh cells	1.8	4.9	16	16	2

As electroporation with frozen cells was successful, transformation with the following cassettes (US20, US21, US30, gM, gO, IE1, pp65) was performed using the frozen electrocompetent cells. Although electroporation time parameters were lower than expected, a great number of colonies was observed after the incubation and positive colonies were obtained for all the target genes (Table 6).

Recombinant virus production and propagation

Once mutants were constructed, we have to produce the defective virus progeny for each target gene. WT and mutant BACbones were used for transfecting HEK 293T and MRC-5 cells using Lipofectamine 2000. Several trials were required to obtain an appropriate BAC concentration from *E. coli*, due to the big size of the BACbone. As an example, Figure 12 shows the transfection efficiency in HEK 293T cells of the WT BAC (A), Δ UL6-HCMV (B) and Δ UL8-HCMV (C) in two different incubation times (48h and 96h). As can be observed, at 48 hours after transfection GFP signal can be appreciated in the culture for all the conditions tested. When comparing both time points, no significant differences are appreciated, however virus production in the Δ UL6-HCMV and in a lesser extent, in Δ UL8-HCMV BACs (Figure 12) is lower compared with the WT control. At both 48 and 96 hours, there was a visible cytopathic effect (CPE) in some of the cells.

Figure 12. Virus production in HEK 293T cells after 48 and 96 hours of incubation. (A) BAC WT; (B) Δ UL6-HCMV; (C) Δ UL8-HCMV

DISCUSSION

To fully characterise the molecular function of HCMV genes, would be necessary to perform time course analysis of the infection ⁴². Therefore, gene deletion mutant studies in comparison with WT virus would allow for the identification of the importance and biological processes in which the protein may be involved ³⁵. Cloning of HCMV genomes as BAC DNA had allowed for a quick and more efficient deletion of target genes in the viral genome. In this work, a rapid method to delete specific genes of HCMV genome have been described and optimised. This method was based on that previously described by Datsenko and Wanner in which chromosomal *E. coli* genes are deleted by using PCR products with an antibiotic resistance gene and homologous tails to the target gene ³⁸. The protocol used for all the transformation process was based on Hollenback, Lyman and Cheng protocol ³⁹, and we have successfully applied this method to generate HCMV mutants.

Here, we have used the Lambda-Red method based on the expression of the Red genes contained into the low copy number plasmid pKD46 ³⁸, that allowed to easily and rapidly

generate mutant HCMV genomes deleting specific genes. The Lambda recombination genes *exo*, *beta* and *gamma* are expressed from the lambda promoter. Those three genes encode enzymes that prevent the degradation of the linear DNA and facilitate the homologous recombination. In addition, pKD46 plasmid exhibits temperature-sensitive replication⁴⁴ and can be easily eliminated from the final mutants by growing at 37°C. Furthermore, the Red system is under the control of an arabinose-dependent inducible promoter which can prevent the undesired recombination events using non-inducing conditions.

Transformation of pKD46 must be done into a strain that already carry the target BAC, otherwise it is not possible to perform the process in the other way around (introduce the BAC into a strain holding pKD46). This fact could be due to a space problem inside the cells, due to the size of the BACbone that may not be allowed to be introduced into a cell that already holds a multicopy plasmid.

The number of colonies obtained and the number of positive colonies for each target gene was different (Figure 9). Taking into account electroporation parameters (Table 4), no pattern can be elucidated for these differences. In this sense, the electroporation parameters may not be crucial to explain the differences between the number of colonies and positive mutants obtained. It seems to be dependent on the target gene. Maybe in some genes the sequence that we used to perform the homologous recombination is more exclusive from this gene and in others is more repetitive and for that we have obtained more false positives.

For the deletion verification, a PCR by using oligonucleotides amplifying from upstream to downstream the gene zone was designed. It is a simple and rapid method to test if recombination occurred and also if the cassette was integrated in the correct location since the size of the WT and the mutant amplicons are different (Figure 8). This validation method has been widely used in different organisms^{44,45,46}. During the screening, some of the colonies seem to contain both WT and mutant gene copy (Figure 8F, H, I, J, P). After a re-transformation assay, a unique band in each lane was observed, indicating that WT BAC contained more than one copy of those genes (Figure 10). For US18 we can conclude that the BAC had 2 more copies of the gene. However, confirmation with more mutants is required.

Although testing PCR works perfectly for almost every deletion verification, in case of pp65 both mutant and WT fragments have too similar sizes making impossible to distinguish among them by this method. For this reason, we carried out an enzymatic restriction of the PCR product by using *KpnI*. With this method, both mutant and WT amplicons were perfectly

distinguished (Figure 11 showing). A useful alternative assay for the deletion testing as long as a specific enzyme for each fragment is available.

Additionally, it was tested whether or not transformation can be performed with frozen electrocompetent cells. According to the literature^{35,47} was absolutely determinant the use of fresh-made electrocompetent cells to obtain a good efficiency during the process. For this purpose, UL8-Kan^R cassette was used for this experiment because it had successfully been transformed and deleted. Surprisingly, the transformation efficiency was much higher when using frozen electrocompetent cells. The use of frozen cells was successfully applied to several target genes with very good results (Table 5). In our hands, we can conclude that this protocol can be easily carried out with frozen electrocompetent cells which speeds up and facilitate the transformation steps, since a stock of electrocompetent cells can be produced and keep frozen that can be further used for several experiments.

WT and mutant BACs were extracted and transfected into HEK 293T in order to generate the viral progeny. Although virus production seems to be lower in the case of mutants comparing with WT, transfection worked well in the three tested conditions (Figure 12). In this way, the differences among the production of WT and mutant viruses could be due to the influence of UL6 and UL8 in the viral replication. Both UL6 and UL8 are genes encoding membrane proteins and belong to RL11 family, whose members seem to be unnecessary for viral growth in cell culture⁴⁸. No function has been described for UL6 gene, while UL8 encodes a highly glycosylated protein that may play a role in the modulation of the immune system, since it reduces the proinflammatory cytokines expression⁴⁹. Because of that, UL8 function seems not to be the reason for its lower production, unless it could play another undescribed function. In case of UL6, as not function have been described, we cannot confirm whether or not is influencing the viral replication. Further studies should be done to elucidate the role of both genes. Despite the successful virus generation in HEK 293T, no infection was detected in MRC-5 after many attempts. The main problem seems to be a low concentration of virus copies, which are insufficient for obtaining virus propagation. For this reason, higher virus concentration needs to be obtained in order to get a proper infection and propagation.

CONCLUSIONS

A rapid method to delete specific genes from HCMV genome was successfully applied and optimised for the first time. We have generated several mutants in both structural and non-structural proteins which reflect the high efficiency and reproducibility of the method. Moreover, although according to literature transformation has to be performed with electrocompetent fresh cells, it was demonstrated that electrocompetent frozen cells also works for transformation with high efficiency which has led to an important improvement of the process.

This work is part of a manuscript that is being prepared for submission.

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INTRODUCTION

Cytomegalovirus is a DNA virus of the Herpesviridae family¹. It is the major cause of mortality in Solid Organ Transplant (SOT) patients and produce congenital infection in neonates². As other Herpesviruses, it can generate latency in human cells. CMV genome includes around 200 predictive Open Reading Frames (ORFs) of which only 60 have a known function, classified as α (immediate Early), β (Early) and γ (Late) genes. Some of the encoded proteins are membrane proteins and are involved in the interaction with the cell receptor during the viral entry, participating in protein complexes: gC-I, including glycoprotein gB, gC-II, formed by gM/gN, gC-III formed by the trimer gH/gL/gO and pentameric complex formed by gH/gL/UL128/UL130/UL131³. Additionally, there are 20 different putative membrane proteins which functions are still unknown. In order to get a better understanding of the function of the membrane proteins during viral cell cycle, we have developed a rapid method for generating HCMV gene deletion mutants by using the λ -Red recombination system and a BAC containing the whole CMV genome have been used to study the viral cycle/infection in the absence of the deleted gene⁴. This knowledge can be used to develop new strategies to fight against CMV infection, and all the associated complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Cassette construction and purification

2. Transformation of *E. coli* DH5 α containing the BAC with pKD46 (Parental Strain)

3. Transformation of *E. coli* DH5 α containing BAC + pKD46 with KanR cassette

4. Deletion verification

5. Viral production by transfection with Lipofectamine

6. Mutant virus propagation

RESULTS

1. Selection of candidate genes for deletion, oligonucleotides and recombinant HCMV generation and verification

Figure 1. Design of primers for cassettes amplification and for deletion testing. Cassette is amplified from pKD4

Figure 2. Proportion of positive and negative colonies from the total obtained for each gene deletion

Figure 3. 1% agarose gel showing the different amplicons obtained in the validation test for each gene deletion. Δ UL6-HCMV and Δ UL8-HCMV are showed

Figure 4. Enzymatic restriction assay for Δ pp65-HCMV testing by using *KpnI*. One band in the lane indicates a Δ pp65-HCMV positive (marked with an arrow), while two bands indicate a WT BAC.

Figure 5. Δ US18-HCMV positive colonies. Colonies obtained during the second transformation in which only one band is observed in each lane.

2. Transformation of UL8-KanR cassette by using frozen cells

V (KW)	Time (ms)	Nº of colonies	Nº of colonies tested	Nº of positive colonies	
Frozen cells	1.8	4.7	190	20	13
Fresh cells	1.8	4.9	16	16	2

Table 1. Electroporation parameters and number of colonies obtained between transformation of UL8-Kan^R cassette by using frozen and fresh electrocompetent cells.

3. Recombinant virus production and propagation

Figure 7. Virus production in HEK 293T cells after 48 and 96 hours of incubation. (A) BAC WT; (B) Δ UL6-HCMV; (C) Δ UL8-HCMV

CONCLUSION

1. A rapid method to delete specific genes from HCMV genome was successfully applied and developed for the first time.
2. Several mutants in both structural and non-structural proteins have been generated.
3. It was demonstrated that electrocompetent frozen cells also works for transformation with high efficiency.

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